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1. Introduction

1.1. Project Overview

Title: BRIDGE (Building Resilient Innovations in Democracy, Governance and Excellence)

Project funder: Horizon Europe (European Commission)

Principal Investigator: Oleksandra Keudel, Kyiv School of Economics

DMP creator & data manager: Illia Tkachenko, Kyiv School of Economics

Project start date: 01-09-2024

Project end date: 31-08-2027

BRIDGE consortium:

Kyiv School of Economics (KSE) – Project lead institution (Coordinator)

Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR) – Expertise in digital democratic innovations

Technical University Berlin (TU Berlin) – Expertise in participatory governance

University of Tartu (UTARTU) – Expertise in digital platforms and data repositories

Associated partner:

Center for Innovation Development (CID) – Expertise in digital democratic innovations in Ukraine

Grant number: 101160337

DMP template: DCC Template

1.2. Project Abstract

The BRIDGE project, funded under the Horizon Europe Program, aims to advance research in participatory governance and digital democratic innovations to address critical challenges in post-war reconstruction in Ukraine. The project explores methods to blend representative and participatory democracy models to achieve efficient and legitimate policy outcomes in crisis situations, particularly focusing on the reconstruction of housing and infrastructure destroyed by the Russian war against Ukraine.

Research activities are centered around two key initiatives:

1. Piloting participatory and deliberative decision-making methods: The project will implement and assess hybrid (on site & digital) citizen assemblies as part of Ukraine's reconstruction process. These assemblies aim to provide inclusive public participation by blending citizens' experiential knowledge with institutional frameworks, ensuring legitimacy and equity in the decision-making process.
2. Evaluating the participatory module eIDEA within the DREAM digital recovery system: DREAM integrates data-driven reconstruction management with participatory governance via the eIDEA module. This module allows for public input and prioritization of recovery projects, emphasizing the role of technology in supporting transparent, inclusive, and accountable governance.

The project's research component is conducted by the BRIDGE consortium which includes Kyiv School of Economics, Erasmus University Rotterdam, Technical University Berlin, University of Tartu, and an associated partner Center for Innovation Development. These partners contribute expertise in digital democratic innovations and participatory governance, ensuring a robust foundation for addressing reconstruction challenges in Ukraine. The outcomes are expected to provide valuable insights for blending participatory and representative democracy in crisis contexts.

2. Data Collection

This research will generate a combination of quantitative survey data, qualitative interview data, and utilise datasets provided by partners. The collected data will be used to evaluate the influence of citizen assemblies on hromada populations and analyze participatory governance processes and digital tools in policy cycles.

2.1. Types and Formats of Data

The project will work with three primary types of data:

Survey data:

- Conducted among the general population of selected hromadas before and after the citizen assembly.
- Responses from assembly participants.
- Quantitative structured datasets in **CSV, XLSX** formats.

Interview and qualitative data:

- In-depth interviews with assembly participants and stakeholders.
- Transcripts and summaries stored as **DOCX, PDF**.
- Audio recordings in **MP3, WAV** formats.

Administrative and secondary data sources:

- Anonymized datasets from external partners (e.g., CID-provided data on participatory governance).
- Open data sources for contextual analysis of hromadas.
- Open data from digital platforms (e.g., DREAM platform).
- Stored in **CSV, XLSX, JSON** formats.

2.2. Data Usability, Storage, and Long-Term Access

The selected formats ensure compatibility with widely used statistical and qualitative analysis software, including Excel, R, Python, NVivo, and ATLAS.ti. These formats facilitate both data sharing and long-term preservation.

To maintain data integrity and accessibility, the research team will:

- Store working datasets on a secure cloud-based repository (**Google Workspace**).
- Anonymized final datasets will be made publicly available on **KSE repository (on GitHub), DSpace (repository of University of Tartu), Discuss Data and Zenodo** for long-term preservation.
- Citizens' assembly participant survey data will be collected both via electronic forms and using **paper-based questionnaires**, to accommodate people with different digital skills (upon their choice). In case of paper-based questionnaires, responses are manually entered into digital formats (Excel, CSV) before being stored in cloud repositories. Depending on the local circumstances, hromada population surveys will be done either via Computer Assisted Personal Interviewing (CAPI) or Computer Assisted Telephone Interviewing (CAPI), so the anonymised data will be collected in a digital format.

2.3. Reuse of Existing Data

This research will incorporate external datasets to enhance analysis and validate findings. The key sources include:

- Partner-provided datasets on participatory governance structures and digital tools.
- Government and municipal open data for demographic, economic, and administrative context.

Where possible, the research will align data collection efforts with existing standards to facilitate comparability and potential integration with other studies.

2.4. Data Collection Methods and Tools

This research involves fieldwork-based surveys, qualitative interviews, focus group studies and external anonymized datasets. A structured approach to data collection, storage, and quality assurance will ensure the integrity and usability of collected data.

2.4.1. Standards and Methodologies

Survey Data:

- The survey will be conducted in person for the citizen assembly participants and in person or via telephone for the hromada population through structured questionnaires administered by trained interviewers.
- In case of paper-based questionnaires, responses will be recorded on paper forms and later digitized into structured Excel (XLSX) or CSV files. Subject to supplier capacity, a CAPI would be used instead of paper-based questionnaires.
- Standardized question phrasing will be used to ensure comparability across responses.

Interview and focus group Data:

- Semi-structured in-depth interviews with citizen assembly participants and stakeholders will follow a predefined thematic guide.
- Focus groups with stakeholders on the usage of digital tools in selected hromadas will follow a predefined guide.
- Responses will be audio-recorded (MP3/WAV), transcribed into DOCX/PDF, and coded using MAXQDA.

External Data:

- Open government datasets and anonymized partner data (e.g., DREAM platform participation data) will be integrated in CSV/XLSX/JSON formats to maintain compatibility.
- This data will provide contextual analysis of participatory trends in hromadas.

Data Processing:

- Survey responses will be manually entered into digital databases following double-entry verification.
- Qualitative data (interview transcriptions) will be structured using thematic coding techniques.
- Statistical tools such as Excel, R, or Python will be used for data cleaning and analysis.

2.4.2. Version Control

Key datasets will be managed using Google Workspace (for internal collaboration), with final versions archived in **KSE repository**, **DSpace**, **Zenodo**, **Discuss Data** for long-term accessibility.

3. Documentation and Metadata

To facilitate data discovery and reuse, we will provide the following metadata:

1. **Descriptive Metadata** – Title, author(s), date of creation, institutional affiliation, keywords, and access conditions.
2. **Structural Metadata** – File format, organization, versioning, and relationships between datasets.
3. **Methodological Metadata** – Data collection methods, analytical procedures, definitions of variables, units of measurement, and assumptions.
4. **Technical Metadata** – Software, tools, or scripts used for data processing.

This metadata will be recorded in **README files, structured metadata files (e.g., XML, JSON), file headers, and an accompanying metadata database.** We will adhere to **Dublin Core, Data Documentation Initiative (DDI), and ISO 19115 (if geospatial data is involved)** to ensure interoperability and discoverability.

4. Ethics and Legal Compliance

To protect the identity of the participants and comply with the ethical norms in accordance with the law on the protection of personal data, international standards, comprehensive methods of protecting the identity of the participants will be applied.

4.1. Participant Anonymization Measures

For the collection, processing and storage of quantitative data, their anonymization will take place, which makes it impossible to identify a person based on the collected data:

- **Complete removal of identifying information:** before processing or publication, all personal data such as name, surname, date of birth, address, contacts and other unique identifiers are removed.
- **Aggregation of data:** personal data are combined into general categories (for example, an age group is indicated instead of an exact age).
- **Generation of random identifiers:** data can be presented in the form of generalized sets or replaced by statistical values without being tied to specific individuals.

For the collection, processing and storage of qualitative data, the data will be pseudonymized, which will confirm the anonymity of the person:

- **Assigning a unique code:** instead of a name or other personal information, a unique digital or alphanumeric identifier is used for storage of citizens' assembly information. For the interview collected on the usage of digital tools in the municipalities, the identifier will be complemented with a generic professional identifier, such as "public official", "civil society representative" **Decryption access:** the key to link the pseudonymized data to the real person is stored separately and accessible only when reasonably necessary.

4.2. Consent Procedures and Data Collection Ethics

Data will be collected by the researchers of Kyiv School of Economics and subcontractors. Before data collection, all participants will be **informed about the purpose of the research, collection, processing, storage of data, contact details of the responsible person or organization**. When applying qualitative methods, written or electronic consent will be obtained in accordance with established legal norms and international standards.

All datasets will be stored in a secure cloud storage (Google Workspace). The **anonymized final datasets** will be publicly available in the KSE repository (on GitHub), DSpace (University of Tartu repository), Zenodo or Discuss Data for long-term preservation.

4.3. Copyright and Intellectual Property Rights

KSE, as a leading research institution within the BRIDGE consortium, retains ownership of the data generated through surveys and research.

To ensure compliance with copyright and Intellectual property rights (IPR), we use a comprehensive approach that includes compliance with current legislation. All materials used within the project are checked for compliance with copyright requirements and license agreements.

1. **Licensed use:** any data protected by copyright in accordance with the norms will be carried out only under the condition of obtaining appropriate licenses, permits or in accordance with the principle of fair use.
2. **Links to sources:** when using third-party information resources, we will ensure proper citation according to international standards (APA, MLA, etc.).

5. Storage and Backup

5.1. Data Storage and Backup Plan

Storage Locations:

- Raw and processed data will be stored on a secure cloud-based repository (**Google Workspace**) with access restricted to the research team. Upon request from the KSE IT team, Google confirmed that the servers used are located within the EU (a copy of the confirmation letter is archived in the project files).

Backup Frequency & Copies:

- Data will be automatically backed up daily in the cloud.
- In the event of data loss or corruption, data will be recovered from **Google Workspace**, which provides automatic backups and version control. This ensures that both raw and processed data can be restored quickly while maintaining data integrity and accessibility.

Responsible Person:

- The project research coordinator will oversee backups.

5.2. Access and Security Management

Data Sensitivity & Security Risks

- The research data includes survey responses and interview transcripts from Ukrainian citizens.
- While data will be anonymized before analysis, risks include unauthorized access, loss, or interception during transfer from the field.

Access Control

- Restricted access: Only authorized project members will have access to the data (see Collaborator Access)
- Secure storage: Data will be stored on a secure cloud-based repository (**Google Workspace**) with access controls.

Secure Data Transfer from the Field

- Survey responses and interview and focus group recordings will be collected on encrypted devices (e.g., tablets or secure USB drives). In case of hiring a contractor, the contractor will provide anonymized datasets.
- Data will be transferred daily or as soon as possible.
- Temporary copies on field devices will be deleted after transfer is confirmed.

Compliance & Best Practices

- The project will follow Horizon Europe's data protection and security guidelines.
- Data handling will align with EU GDPR standards for research ethics and security.
- Sensitive data (e.g., interview transcripts before anonymization) will be stored separately and encrypted.

Collaborator Access

- Consortium partners will have controlled access to processed, anonymized data only.
- No personal identifiers will be shared beyond the KSE research team.

This approach ensures confidentiality, integrity, and secure management of research data while aligning with EU research standards.

6. Selection and Preservation

To ensure compliance with contractual, legal, and regulatory requirements, data will be managed according to institutional policies and relevant legal frameworks (e.g., GDPR, research ethics guidelines).

6.1. Long-term data retention and preservation

Retention and Disposal Requirements

- Data subject to legal or contractual obligations will be retained for the required period and securely deleted when no longer needed.
- Personally identifiable or sensitive data will be anonymized or destroyed according to ethical and security guidelines.

Selection Criteria for Retention

- Data will be retained based on its **scientific value, potential for reuse, and ethical considerations**.
- Key datasets necessary for **validating findings, conducting further research, and supporting teaching** will be prioritized for long-term storage.

Foreseeable Research Uses

- **During the project and after its completion**, anonymized data can be publicly published to support further research and ensure broader accessibility.
- The data may be used for **longitudinal studies, comparative research, and policy evaluations**.
- It may also **serve as a resource for secondary analysis, replication studies, and methodological advancements**.

Preservation and Duration

- Essential datasets will be archived for a minimum of **5 years** in **institutional or domain-specific repositories** to ensure long-term accessibility.
- Preservation measures will include **regular format conversion, metadata updates, and redundancy checks** to maintain data integrity.

By implementing these strategies, the data will remain accessible, usable, and secure for future research and academic contributions.

6.2. Data Archiving Procedures

Repository Selection

- The data will be stored in the **Google Workspace repository with restricted access for the research team**, ensuring secure and controlled data management.
- Publicly available anonymized datasets will be deposited in **open-access repositories (e.g., Discuss Data, Zenodo, ICPSR (Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research))** to facilitate broader research use.

Costs and Funding

- The use of **Google Workspace** does not incur direct costs, as it is managed within institutional infrastructure.
- If external repositories are used for public data sharing, any associated costs will be covered through **institutional funding or project grants**. The Consortium will prioritize free-of-charge dedicated research repositories, such as **Discuss Data and Zenodo**.

Preparation for Sharing and Preservation

- Time and effort for data preparation, including **metadata creation, anonymization, file format conversion, and documentation**, have been accounted for in the project timeline.
- The project can cover working hours of researchers to **manage the repository, ensure proper documentation, and later create an open and understandable repository for researchers worldwide**.
- Resources will be allocated to ensure compliance with best practices for data curation, version control, and long-term preservation.

7. Data Sharing

Potential data users will be informed about anonymized and processed data through channels such as institutional websites and relevant online repositories. However, no personally identifiable information will be shared outside of the KSE research team.

7.1. Data recipients

The data will be shared with various stakeholders who may benefit from its use, including:

- Researchers, academics, students engaged in research activities in various disciplines who can use data to confirm conclusions, conduct comparative studies or develop new methodologies.
- Academic Institutions, Universities, think tanks and educational organizations that can integrate data into research projects, educational materials, or collaborative initiatives.

- Government Agencies and policymakers that can use data to inform policy decisions, regulatory frameworks and evidence-based planning.
- Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) operating in various sectors that can use data to support their missions and initiatives.

7.2. Terms of access and use of data

To maintain data integrity, security and ethical standards, access to data will be subject to the following conditions:

- Compliance with ethical and legal standards. Users must comply with all ethical guidelines, data protection regulations and institutional data use requirements.
- Notation of authorship and citation. Any use of the data set must be properly explained, including reference to the original authors, project, and source of the data in publications, presentations.
- Restrictions on modification and redistribution of data. Users will not be allowed to modify, distort or redistribute the data without prior permission.

By implementing these terms, data sharing will be managed responsibly, ensuring compliance with ethical considerations, regulations and fostering collaboration while maintaining data integrity. The data will be provided through a reliable online repository of the Kyiv School of Economics, which ensures long-term availability and proper data management.

The data will be available after the primary analysis is completed and the results of the primary study are published. This ensures that the data is well documented, validated and properly formatted before release. An estimated release date will be provided according to the main project milestones.

The dataset will be assigned a **digital identifier**, widely used and internationally recognized standard for referencing datasets, research articles and digital resources. Assigning an PID will improve:

- Citations and academic recognition: researchers using the dataset can properly cite it in their publications, increasing the impact and visibility of the dataset.
- Long-term availability – even if the storage location of the data set changes, PID ensures constant access through redirection mechanisms.

7.3. Restrictions on Data Sharing

All data will be **anonymized to facilitate safe and ethical data sharing while eliminating potential restrictions**. De-identification involves the removal of identifying information to prevent identification of individuals in a data set (e.g. names, addresses, numbers, etc.), summarizing or aggregating data to prevent re-identification. This will promote compliance with ethical and legal standards and allow data to be shared without violating privacy laws.

We require exclusive access to the data for a period of analysis conduction to ensure the integrity and validity of our research prior to release. This period depends on project milestones. This exclusivity allows sufficient time for analysis, quality assurance and any necessary regulatory

compliance before wider distribution. During this period, the raw data will be available and processed exclusively by researchers of the Kyiv School of Economics, and anonymized data can be accessed by other researchers in the Consortium for joint analysis and validation.

8. Responsibilities and Resources

8.1. Roles and Responsibilities in Data Management

The Project Research Coordinator at KSE will oversee the implementation, review, and revision of the DMP.

Responsibilities:

- **Data Collection & Entry:** KSE research team and subcontractors (survey, focus group and interview data).
- **Data Quality & Processing:** Research team at KSE.
- **Storage & Backup:** Research team at KSE (Google Workspace).
- **Security & Access Control:** Project Research Coordinator ensures compliance with Horizon Europe guidelines and GDPR.
- **Data Sharing & Archiving:** KSE research team, following BRIDGE consortium agreements.

Responsibilities are defined in the consortium agreement, with KSE managing data handling and consortium partners accessing only anonymized datasets.

8.2. Required Resources

Resources Required

- **Software & Tools:** Standard data analysis tools (Excel, R, Python, NVivo, ATLAS.ti, MAXQDA) are sufficient; no additional purchases required.
- **Hardware:** Encrypted storage devices (USB drives, external hard drives) for secure field data transfer.
- **Training:** Basic training for field researchers on data entry accuracy, anonymization, and secure transfer. Workshop for the researchers in the consortium on aligning implementation approaches to academic integrity.
- **Storage & Backup:** Institutional cloud storage on **Google Workspace**); no additional charges expected.
- **Data Repository Costs:** Zenodo, Discuss Data (free for open access), but potential costs if using alternative repositories.

No major additional resources are expected beyond standard institutional provisions.